

Time-Modulated Dynamic Arrays for Integrated Communication and Sensing: A Review of Opportunities, System Considerations, and Challenges

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ABSTRACT Time-modulated arrays (TMAs) utilize time as an alternative beamforming method to augment existing analog/digital/hybrid wireless beamformers. The introduction of the time dimension in such dynamic antenna arrays may offer advantageous beamforming capabilities to emerging integrated sensing and communication (ISAC) applications, dramatically reducing the hardware complexity of their implementations. This article reviews the state-of-the-art TMAs, with an emphasis on those reported in integrated-circuit (IC) technologies, such as complementary metal–oxide–semiconductor (CMOS), for wireless applications. Starting with an analytical framework of TMAs, their operation and beamforming characteristics are analyzed for multiple periodic switching schemes, including the ON/OFF amplitude-modulation scheme, the continuously ON 0°/180° phase-modulation scheme, and the double switching scheme with even/odd-symmetry. Then, a survey of the main IC applications in which TMAs have been proposed is presented, including their ISAC applications in transmitter (TX) concurrent multibeam generation, reflective relays that support multibeam reception and transmission, spatiotemporal filtering that can be used for sensing, and receiver multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) using one-wire interface and enhancing physical layer security in wireless communication. Afterward, the performance characteristics of TMAs for both receiving and transmitting beamforming arrays are analyzed and compared with standard single-beam and multibeam phased arrays. Finally, the potential challenges of TMAs, including the fixed-angle nature of their beams and the generated harmonics impact especially for TX arrays, are discussed.

INDEX TERMS Antenna beamforming, complementary metal–oxide–semiconductor (CMOS), integrated sensing and communication (ISAC), multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) communication, phased array, radar, secure communication, spatiotemporal filtering, time-modulated array (TMA).

INTRODUCTION

Time-modulated arrays (TMAs) utilize the time dimension as an additional design degree of freedom to control the radiation characteristics of antenna arrays. They were first introduced in 1959, in which the time parameter was used as an additional variable to propose a 4-D electromagnetic radiator that is periodically modulated in time with periodic time sequences [1]. Following that, in 1961, TMAs were proposed for simultaneous multibeam

scanning based on their radiated harmonics [2]. In addition, in 1963, a receiving TMA was experimentally validated to achieve ultralow sidelobe levels that are below -40 dB, enabled by programming the time-modulation switches [3]. Despite the promising features and properties of TMAs [4], they did not remarkably receive considerable research interest soon afterward, and they were only used in some limited applications such as radio-astronomy [5]. Possible reasons are: 1) the inefficient capabilities

of the slow and lossy RF switches at that time that could not meet the growing demand for wideband systems; and 2) the lack of advanced digital signal processing (DSP) design methodologies that are capable of arbitrarily defining the ON/OFF time sequences of the time modulation operation to deal with the unavoidable and undesired harmonics generated by TMAs, resulting in significant power losses and interferences.

Since the beginning of this century, TMAs have again gained considerable research interest with the technological advancements achieved in the speed of RF switches and DSP algorithms. In particular, in [6], a differential evolution algorithm was utilized to optimize the ON-time instants of the TMA's switches along with the static excitation amplitudes of the antenna array elements to achieve ultralow sidelobe levels and suppressed sidebands. Following that, significant research based on optimization algorithms have been applied to TMAs, including simulated annealing [7], simple genetic algorithm [8], differential evolution [9], [10], particle swarm optimization [11], iterative convex algorithm [12], [13], two-stage convex algorithm [14], multiobjective optimization [15], and hybrid algorithms such as artificial bee colony differential evolution [16], particle swarm optimization with wavelet mutation [17], and others [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26]. Further, in addition to conventional linear TMAs, further research has been conducted on planar arrays [27], [28], [29], [30], nonuniform arrays [31], circular arrays [32], [33], [34], and sparse arrays [35]. As a result, TMAs have been widely utilized in many applications [36], [37], including multibeam scanning [38], [39], [40], multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO) radar [41], orbital-angular-momentum arrays [42], [43], direction-of-arrival estimation [44], [45], [46], secure communication [47], [48], wireless power transmission [49], [50], and antenna array calibrations [51].

With their electronic beam steering capabilities, phased arrays are at the heart of the hardware integrated-circuit (IC) implementations of most of today's wireless applications at both mm-Wave and sub-terahertz (THz) frequencies [52], [53], [54], [55], [56], [57], [58], [59], [60], [61], [62], [63], [64], [65], relying on high-quality integrated phase shifters (PSs) [66], [67], [68], compact microwave passives [69], [70], and high-performance variable gain blocks [71], [72], [73]. Nevertheless, enabled by the high speed and performance of the RF switches that modern IC technologies, such as complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS), offer, TMAs have recently gained dramatically growing research interest in advanced IC technologies, as shown in Fig. 1, with applications in MIMO communication [74], [75], concurrent multi-beam generation for integrated sensing and communication (ISAC) applications [76], multibeam relays with ISAC capabilities [77], physical layer security [78], [79], power amplifier (PA)'s back-off efficiency enhancement [80], and spatiotemporal filtering to synthesize highly customized shapes of radiation patterns [81]. As recent examples, using GlobalFoundries 22-nm CMOS SOI, the works in [76] and [77] demonstrated time-modulation switching speeds of 2 and 1 GHz, respectively, with corresponding maximum symbol modulation rates

FIG. 1. Evolution of TMAs over the years.

of 1 and 0.5 GHz for TMA-based ISAC systems. In addition, the work in [74] demonstrated in GlobalFoundries 45-nm CMOS SOI a time-modulation switching speed of 200 MHz with a corresponding symbol modulation rate of 100 MHz. Further, utilizing the high-speed and dense digital circuitry that advanced IC technologies, such as CMOS, offer benefiting from scaling, full IC-based integrations can also have the potential to implement previously proposed advanced TMA algorithms for sideband suppression [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26] with low complexity. To study this growing demand of TMAs in IC technologies, this article reviews the TMAs' basics, potential applications, beamforming characteristics, and technical challenges, with an emphasis on IC implementations.

The rest of this review is organized as follows. "Analysis of TMAs" section analyzes the theory of TMAs operating with basic time-modulation schemes, including the ON/OFF amplitude-modulation (AM) scheme, the continuously ON $0^\circ/180^\circ$ phase-modulation (PM) scheme, and the double switching scheme with even/odd-symmetry. "Proposed ISAC Applications in CMOS" section reviews the potential applications in which TMAs have been proposed utilizing IC implementations, especially for ISAC applications. "Performance Characteristics of RX TMA" section analyzes the noise behavior of receiver (RX) TMAs and compares their beamforming characteristics with other standard single-beam and multibeam RX phased arrays. "Performance Characteristics of TX TMA" section compares the performance metrics of transmitter (TX) TMAs with other standard single-beam and multibeam TX phased arrays. "Technical Challenges and Future Works" section discusses some of the technical challenges of TMAs and accordingly suggests some future research directions. Finally, "Conclusion" section draws some conclusions.

ANALYSIS OF TMAS

The beamforming characteristics of TMAs can be revealed by analyzing their array factor. Without loss of generality, we consider in this section an N -element TMA operating in an RX, while noting that its beamforming characteristics (that are to be derived) hold as well for TMAs operating in TXs by reciprocity. The N -element RX TMA to be analyzed is shown in

FIG. 2. System architecture of an N -element RX TMA with $\lambda/2$ -spacing between the antenna elements.

Fig. 2. The spacing between the antennas (d) is assumed to be $\lambda/2$, where λ is the free-space wavelength at the operating RF center frequency (f_{RF}). In addition, the N elements of the array (from $m = 1$ to $m = N$) are assumed to be periodically modulated in time by the waveforms $W_1(t)$ to $W_N(t)$. Assuming that the gain of the RX's front-end is unity and that the RX receives a plane wave whose phase propagation constant is k ($k = 2\pi/\lambda$) and has a sinusoidal dependence with frequency f_{RF} ($e^{j2\pi f_{\text{RF}}t}$), the overall array output ($A(\theta, t)$) of the RX TMA at the combining node R can be expressed as

$$A(\theta, t) = \sum_{m=1}^N W_m(t) e^{jk(m-1)d \sin \theta} e^{j2\pi f_{\text{RF}}t} \quad (1)$$

where θ is the angle measured from the broadside direction of the antenna array. Given the periodicity of $W_m(t)$, it can be expanded using Fourier series as

$$W_m(t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} a_n e^{j2\pi n f_{\text{TM}}t} \quad (2)$$

where f_{TM} is the time-modulation frequency ($f_{\text{TM}} = 1/T_{\text{TM}}$) and a_n are the Fourier series coefficients, which can be expressed as

$$a_n = \frac{1}{T_{\text{TM}}} \int_{T_{\text{TM}}} W_m(t) e^{-j2\pi n f_{\text{TM}}t} dt. \quad (3)$$

By substituting (2) into (1), $A(\theta, t)$ can be further expressed as

$$A(\theta, t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{m=1}^N a_n e^{jk(m-1)d \sin \theta} \right) e^{j2\pi(f_{\text{RF}} + n f_{\text{TM}})t} \quad (4)$$

which reduces to

$$A(\theta, t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} H_n e^{j\psi} e^{j2\pi(f_{\text{RF}} + n f_{\text{TM}})t} \quad (5)$$

where H_n and ψ are, respectively, given by

$$H_n = \left| \sum_{m=1}^N a_n e^{jk(m-1)d \sin \theta} \right| \quad (6)$$

$$\psi = \angle \sum_{m=1}^N a_n e^{jk(m-1)d \sin \theta}. \quad (7)$$

We now consider some cases for the time-modulation clocks $W_m(t)$, and study their associated beamforming characteristics by analyzing their corresponding array factor's magnitude (H_n).

ON/OFF AM Switching

For the case of a periodic ON/OFF AM switching scheme, in which the N elements of the array are sequentially modulated in a nonoverlapping manner and each element is only turned ON for $1/N$ of the time-modulation period (T_{TM}) as shown in Fig. 3(a), $W_m(t)$ can be expressed as

$$W_m(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \frac{(m-1)T_{\text{TM}}}{N} \leq t \leq \frac{mT_{\text{TM}}}{N} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Accordingly, by calculating a_n using (3) and then substituting in (6), $H_{n,\text{AM}}$ can be finally derived as

$$H_{n,\text{AM}} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{N} \frac{\sin\left(\frac{N\pi}{2} \sin \theta\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \sin \theta\right)}, & n = 0 \\ \frac{\sin(\pi n/N) \sin\left(\frac{N\pi}{2} \left(\sin \theta - \frac{2n}{N}\right)\right)}{\pi n \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \left(\sin \theta - \frac{2n}{N}\right)\right)}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

The expression of $H_{n,\text{AM}}$ suggests that $(N + 1)$ different incident signals, at the same f_{RF} , from the angles $\theta = \sin^{-1}(2n/N)$ (where $n = 0, \pm 1, \dots, \pm N/2$) can be concurrently received, mapped, and frequency-multiplexed at the combining node R to different frequency components $f_{\text{RF}} \pm n f_{\text{TM}}$. As an example, Fig. 4(a) shows the array factor of the five radiation patterns ($n = 0, \pm 1$, and ± 2) for a four-element TMA operating with an ON/OFF AM switching scheme. As can be seen by the results, the peaks of the radiation patterns occur at $\theta = 0^\circ, \pm 30^\circ$, and $\pm 90^\circ$ with an infinite cross isolation among the different radiations.

Continuously on $0^\circ/180^\circ$ PM Switching

Instead of turning OFF the array elements during the time-modulation operation, they can be maintained continuously ON while sequentially time modulating their phase between 0° and 180° as shown in Fig. 3(b), where $W_m(t)$ is given by

$$W_m(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \frac{(m-1)T_{\text{TM}}}{N} \leq t \leq \frac{mT_{\text{TM}}}{N} \\ -1, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

FIG. 3. Waveforms of the TMA clocks with: (a) ON/OFF AM scheme; (b) continuously on $0^\circ/180^\circ$ PM scheme; (c) ON/OFF AM scheme with double even switching; and (d) ON/OFF AM scheme with double odd switching.

FIG. 4. Array factor simulation results of a four-element RX TMA with: (a) ON/OFF AM scheme; (b) continuously on $0^\circ/180^\circ$ PM scheme; (c) ON/OFF AM scheme with double even switching; and (d) ON/OFF AM scheme with double odd switching.

For this PM switching scheme, $H_{n,PM}$ can be derived using (3) and (6) as

$$H_{n,PM} = \begin{cases} \left(1 - \frac{2}{N}\right) \frac{\sin\left(\frac{N\pi}{2} \sin\theta\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \sin\theta\right)}, & n = 0 \\ 2 \frac{\sin(\pi n/N) \sin\left(\frac{N\pi}{2} \left(\sin\theta - \frac{2n}{N}\right)\right)}{\pi n \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \left(\sin\theta - \frac{2n}{N}\right)\right)}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

The expression of $H_{n,PM}$ suggests that the PM switching scheme exhibits similar beamforming characteristic to the AM switching scheme, except that it offers an improved array factor with a ratio of $N(1 - (2/N))$ for ($n = 0$) and 2 for all the other radiation patterns ($n \neq 0$). As an example, Fig. 4(b) shows the array factor of the five radiation patterns ($n = 0, \pm 1$, and ± 2) for a four-element TMA operating with a $0^\circ/180^\circ$ PM switching scheme, showing an improved array factor of ~ 6 dB for the five radiation patterns compared to the AM-switching scheme.

Double Switching With Even/Odd-Symmetry

Double switching per time-modulation clock with even (odd)-symmetry can be utilized to eliminate the odd (even) complex harmonics, while enhancing the array factor of the even (odd) harmonics by a factor of 2. For the case of double switching

with even-symmetry [shown in Fig. 3(c)], $W_m(t)$ can be expressed as

$$W_m(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \frac{(m-1)T_{TM}}{N} \leq t \leq \frac{mT_{TM}}{N} \\ 1, & \text{if } \frac{T_{TM}}{2} + \frac{(m-1)T_{TM}}{N} \leq t \leq \frac{T_{TM}}{2} + \frac{mT_{TM}}{N} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

and has the associated $H_{n,even}$, which is given by

$$H_{n,even} = \begin{cases} 2H_{n,AM}, & n \text{ even} \\ 0, & n \text{ odd.} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

On the other hand, for the case of double switching with odd-symmetry [shown in Fig. 3(d)], $W_m(t)$ can be expressed as

$$W_m(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \frac{(m-1)T_{TM}}{N} \leq t \leq \frac{mT_{TM}}{N} \\ -1, & \text{if } \frac{T_{TM}}{2} + \frac{(m-1)T_{TM}}{N} \leq t \leq \frac{T_{TM}}{2} + \frac{mT_{TM}}{N} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

and has the associated $H_{n,odd}$, which is given by

$$H_{n,odd} = \begin{cases} 2H_{n,AM}, & n \text{ odd} \\ 0, & n \text{ even.} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

As an example, Fig. 4(c) and (d) shows the array factors of the five radiation patterns ($n = 0, \pm 1$, and ± 2) for a four-element

FIG. 5. Chip micrographs of the state-of-the-art TMA CMOS implementations: (a) D-band four-element MIMO TX TMA with 20 concurrent beams in GlobalFoundries 22-nm CMOS SOI [76]; (b) D-band eight-element multibeam reflective relay array based on TMA in GlobalFoundries 22-nm CMOS SOI [77]; (c) 28-GHz four-element MIMO RX TMA in GlobalFoundries 45-nm CMOS SOI [74]; (d) 28-GHz four-element MIMO RX array utilizing phase shifters' time modulation in 65-nm CMOS [75]; (e) 71–76-GHz four-element TX TMA with physical layer security in 65-nm CMOS [78]; and (f) 28-GHz two-element TX TMA with physical layer security in 65-nm CMOS [79].

TMA operating with a double switching scheme with even and odd symmetries, respectively. As can be seen by the results, for the case of an even (odd) symmetry, the odd (even) harmonics are eliminated, and the array factor of the even (odd) harmonics is enhanced by ~ 6 dB compared to the standard AM-switching scheme.

As a summary, the ON/OFF AM switching scheme offers the simplest switching approach. However, due to the OFF periods, the array aperture is not fully utilized at any given time instant, resulting in a loss in the array's gain. This issue can be resolved by the $0^\circ/180^\circ$ PM switching scheme given its continuously ON operation. However, the implementation complexity of the $0^\circ/180^\circ$ PM switching scheme is more severe than that of the ON/OFF AM switching scheme as the former requires dynamic yet precise $0^\circ/180^\circ$ phase switching with the speed of the time-modulation clocks. Finally, on top of both AM/PM switching approaches, the double switching scheme with even/odd-symmetry may be utilized to suppress selective harmonics, if needed, relaxing the filtering requirements. However, this advantage comes at the cost of more complex switching logic that is required to precisely control the characteristics of the time-modulation clocks of the array elements.

PROPOSED ISAC APPLICATIONS IN CMOS

This section reviews the potential applications for ISAC, in which TMAs have been proposed and demonstrated utilizing

full integration in silicon-based ICs. These applications include TX concurrent multibeam generation, reflective relays that support multibeam reception and transmission, and spatiotemporal filtering that can be used for sensing, as well as RX MIMO using one-wire interface and enhancing physical layer security in wireless communication. Finally, PA back-off efficiency enhancement is discussed to improve the TX efficiency.

TX Concurrent Multibeam Generation

Conventional analog beamforming arrays require multiple independent beamformers to generate multiple beams, leading to high hardware complexities. By leveraging a hybrid static/dynamic TMA beamforming architecture, a concurrent 20-beam MIMO TX array architecture has recently been proposed at D-band and implemented in GlobalFoundries 22-nm CMOS SOI [76], as shown in Fig. 5(a). It combines a 4×4 Butler-matrix-based static beamformer with a four-element dynamic TMA to effectively multiply the number of beams without increasing the array size or the number of RF chains, offering much lower hardware complexity than having 20 parallel analog beamformers with PSs. Through this beam-multiplication technique, concurrent transmission of independent beams at distinct carrier frequencies is achieved, making use of the TMA sidebands and enabling efficient joint communication and sensing capabilities. Further, the architecture can be scaled to generate larger number of beams for greater

capacity by increasing the size of the TMA array and the Butler-matrix proportionally. This architecture is especially expected to be promising for emerging applications requiring high link throughputs, rapid situational awareness, and simultaneous multibeam communication, such as distributed MIMO networks and MIMO radar systems.

Multibeam Reflective Relays

The envisioned 6G distributed MIMO (D-MIMO) networks for fronthaul mobile communication and advanced factory automation require ISAC capabilities. In such applications, multiple fixed-location distributed units (DUs) are required to communicate with multiple fixed-location radio units (RUs), and low-latency two-way communication combined with sensing is therefore the key to ensure high data rate and RUs' timing synchronization, so that the network of RUs can form coherent distributed MIMOs with mobile user equipments (UEs). To address this demand, the work in [77] presents a scalable D-band active reflective relay array architecture that can enable nonline-of-sight (NLOS) wireless communication links with multibeam reception and broadcasting capabilities. It combines two TMAs at the receiving and transmitting front-ends of the relay, which utilizes: 1) the RX TMA sidebands for multibeam reception from multiple external TX wireless nodes; and 2) the TX TMA sidebands for broadcasting the received data streams out to multiple external RX wireless nodes in different directions. Compared to standard multibeam relay architectures, this TMA relay architecture works on-the-fly without any up/down-converters, reducing the power consumption and enabling low-latency communication with high array scalability. However, this comes at the cost of fixed angles of reception and transmission, yet this is not considered problematic for the 6G D-MIMO applications as they are mostly based on fixed wireless nodes. To demonstrate the proposed TMA architecture with a hardware prototype, [77] reports an eight-element 120-GHz relay array in GlobalFoundries CMOS SOI, which is shown in Fig. 5(b).

Spatiotemporal Filtering

By utilizing the rapid-beam switching capabilities of modern CMOS-based phased arrays, the time-modulation operation may offer spatiotemporal filtering capabilities to synthesize complex beam patterns that are otherwise infeasible due to limited phase/gain controllability [81]. Based on 28-GHz phased-array ICs, [81] demonstrates highly customized beam shapes such as sidelobe-suppressed radiation patterns, multi-armed beams, and patterns with synthesized deep nulls, which are all achieved by time-multiplexing the operation between different spatial beams and averaging their contributions over time. One of the advantages of this technique for large-scale arrays is that it does not rely on precise phase or gain controls from each array element, making it especially attractive for low cost, large-scale arrays where hardware resolutions are limited. However, it requires baseband filtering to deal with the frequency domain spurs that result from beam switching, and also has modulation bandwidth limitations that arise from

the large required oversampling ratios, which is especially challenging if considered for 5G mm-Wave that requires modulation bandwidths up to 800 MHz.

RX MIMO Using One-Wire Interface

As studied in "Analysis of TMAs" section, $(N + 1)$ concurrent incident signals (at the same center frequency f_{RF}) from different angles in the space $\theta = \sin^{-1}(2n/N)$ can be received and mapped by an N -element TMA to different frequency components $f_{RF} \pm nf_{TM}$, where $n = 0, \pm 1, \dots, \pm N/2$. Utilizing this space-to-spectrum mapping property, TMAs may enable highly efficient MIMO RX architectures, making use of the TMA sidebands to map different angles to different frequencies. As shown in Fig. 5(c), the use of a TMA-based beamformer combined with one-wire interface is demonstrated in [74] based on a five-beam 28-GHz four-element RX TMA in GlobalFoundries 45-nm CMOS SOI. The TMA switching frequency of this work is chosen sufficiently larger than the modulation bandwidth to satisfy the Nyquist criteria and maintain the cross-beam isolation. In addition, besides the TMA operation, PSs are utilized to provide the capability of steering all the beams together. Compared to other MIMO approaches based on fully connected phased arrays, the spatially multiplexed RX MIMO architecture using TMA is simpler, and has lower hardware complexity and lower dc power consumption. However, they require analog-to-digital converters (ADCs) with larger dynamic range to sustain the frequency-multiplexed beams, and either require tunable analog filters or sophisticated digital back-ends to demodulate the data streams. As an extension of this TMA architecture, as shown in Fig. 5(d), a 28-GHz four-beam MIMO RX phased array is implemented in 65-nm CMOS based on a Nyquist-rate fast-beam switching, which is achieved by time modulating the PSs of the array in synchronous with switching the demodulation chains [75].

Physical Layer Security

Physical layer security has become a critical consideration for next-generation wireless communication systems. Conventional phased arrays strive to offer some degree of security through directional transmission, but the issue of side-lobe leakage remains a vulnerability. By dynamically varying the transmitted waveforms in space and time, a four-element TX TMA with physical layer security is reported in [78] across 71–76 GHz and implemented in 65-nm CMOS, as shown in Fig. 5(e). At unintended directions, the received signal experiences spectral aliasing and constellation scrambling, preventing eavesdropping. This way, the physical layer security serves as a powerful complementary layer of defense for traditional cryptographic methods, where spatial scrambling and time modulation act as a first line of defense, reducing the chances of a successful attack even before cryptographic layers are attempted.

PA Back-Off Efficiency Enhancement

Traditional mm-Wave PAs tend to suffer from significant degradations in efficiency at power back-off regions, which is a major bottleneck for high-order modulation schemes that are

FIG. 6. Noise analysis model of an N -element RX TMA with AM scheme.

common in today's wireless applications. To address this issue, a two-element TX TMA with physical layer security is reported at 28 GHz in [79] and implemented in 65-nm CMOS, as shown in Fig. 5(f). It demonstrates that by introducing time modulation into fully connected phased-array TXs, it is not only feasible to secure wireless links but also to mitigate the multibeam peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR) issue utilizing the fact that time modulation avoids coherent summation of power. This way, each PA only experiences the PAPR of a single beam and is therefore allowed to operate closer to its saturation point, enhancing the efficiency of PAs. Another 24-GHz direct-digital beamforming TX with time-modulation operation is proposed in [80] and implemented in a 0.18- μm SiGe technology. By engineering the time-modulation switching controls of multiple PA elements, the reported TX eliminates the undesirable radiated harmonics with efficient power back-off management, offering a scalable solution for future high-efficiency and high-capacity mm-Wave TXs.

PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS OF RX TMA

In this section, we attempt to analyze the performance characteristics of RX TMAs. Toward this goal, we first analyze their noise behavior. Then, we compare RX TMAs with other standard single-beam and multibeam analog/digital beamformers that are based on phased arrays.

Noise Analysis of RX TMA

The noise behavior of an N -element RX TMA can be analyzed utilizing the analysis framework in Fig. 6. As an example, the analysis is carried out assuming an AM switching scheme. However, the same analysis flow and results can be applied to other TMA switching schemes as well. We make the following assumptions throughout the analysis: 1) the noise contribution of the time-modulation switch is assumed to be negligible, which is a reasonable assumption to make assuming a sufficiently large RX gain before the switch; 2) the noise random

process of the elements is stationary (i.e., its statistics do not change over time); and 3) the noise sources of the N channels $[n_1(t), n_2(t), \dots, \text{and } n_N(t)]$ belong to the same random process $n(t)$ that is white and has a double-sided power spectral density of P_n . We first derive the noise power spectral density at the outputs of the elements (nodes $E_1, E_2, \dots, \text{and } E_N$), and based on that finally derive the noise power spectral density at the combining node R .

In the time domain, the noise at node E_1 can be expressed as

$$E_1(t) = n_1(t)W_1(t). \quad (16)$$

Since the noise $n_1(t)$ is a random process and the time-modulation waveform $W_1(t)$ is a deterministic signal, and $E_1(t)$ is generally random. Therefore, the power spectral density of $E_1(t)$ can be derived by first calculating its autocorrelation function $[R_{E_1}(t, t + \tau)]$, and then computing the Fourier transform of $R_{E_1}(t, t + \tau)$. The autocorrelation function $R_{E_1}(t, t + \tau)$ can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} R_{E_1}(t, t + \tau) &= E[E_1(t)E_1(t + \tau)] \\ &= E[n_1(t)n_1(t + \tau)W_1(t)W_1(t + \tau)]. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Since $W_1(t)$ is deterministic, it is independent of the expectation operator, and accordingly $R_{E_1}(t, t + \tau)$ can be simplified to

$$R_{E_1}(t, t + \tau) = W_1(t)W_1(t + \tau)R_{n_1}(t, t + \tau). \quad (18)$$

Under the assumption that $n_1(t)$ is stationary, its autocorrelation function $R_{n_1}(t, t + \tau)$ is independent of t and only depends on the time difference τ . Moreover, since $n_1(t)$ is white, its autocorrelation function is simply a Dirac delta function that is weighted by its power spectral density (P_n). Thus, $R_{E_1}(t, t + \tau)$ can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} R_{E_1}(t, t + \tau) &= W_1(t)W_1(t + \tau)P_n\delta(\tau) \\ &= W_1^2(t)P_n\delta(\tau). \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

The power spectral density $S_{E_1}(f)$ of $E_1(t)$ can now be derived by calculating the Fourier transform of $R_{E_1}(t, t + \tau)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{E_1}(f) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} W_1^2(t)P_n\delta(\tau)e^{-j2\pi f\tau} d\tau \\ &= W_1^2(t)P_n \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

that is periodic with a period of T_{TM} and can be expressed for one period of T_{TM} as

$$S_{E_1}(f) = \begin{cases} P_n, & \text{if } 0 \leq t \leq \frac{T_{TM}}{N} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

Given the periodicity of $S_{E_1}(f)$, the random process at node E_1 is concluded to be cyclostationary with a power spectral density that toggles between P_n (for $1/N$ of the time) and 0 [for $(N - 1)/N$ of the time]. Similarly, the same analysis can be repeated for the outputs of the other elements (E_2, E_3, \dots, E_N) concluding that they also exhibit cyclostationary random processes with a period of T_{TM} and with the power spectral

FIG. 7. Architectures of the different RX beamforming systems included in the reported comparison.

density of the m th element (at node E_m) given by

$$S_{E_m}(f) = W_m^2(t)P_n = \begin{cases} P_n, & \text{if } \frac{(m-1)T_{\text{TM}}}{N} \leq t \leq \frac{mT_{\text{TM}}}{N} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

By summing the power spectral densities of the N elements, the noise autocorrelation function at the combining node (node R) can be derived as

$$R_R(t, t + \tau) = (W_1^2(t) + W_2^2(t) + \dots + W_N^2(t))P_n\delta(\tau) = P_n\delta(\tau) \quad (23)$$

which is stationary and has a double-sided power spectral density of P_n . Interestingly, it can be concluded that although the noise random processes at nodes E_1, E_2, \dots, E_N are cyclostationary, the noise random process at the combining node R is stationary and exhibits the same power spectral density as the noise of only one element (before the time-modulation switch). This can be intuitively justified in the time-domain, as shown in Fig. 6, by noting that the combining node R is only affected by one noise contribution of only one of the N elements at any time instant.

RX TMA Versus Standard Beamformers

A performance comparison is performed between RX TMAs and other standard single-beam and multibeam analog/digital RX beamformers. The main performance metrics that are being considered in this comparison are the number of

concurrent beams, the overall throughput of each architecture, the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) per beam after beamforming, and the hardware implementation complexity. As shown in Fig. 7, six architectures are considered in the comparison: a single-element RX with an SNR of SNR_{Base} (taken as a baseline implementation), an N -element single-beam beamformer, an N -element analog beamformer with M subarrays, a fully connected N -element analog beamformer with M beams, a digital N -element beamformer with M beams, and an N -element TMA with AM switching. For the RX TMA, two cases are considered: case 1 where the bandwidth per beam is maintained as BW/N so that the overall occupied bandwidth of the RX TMA is similar to that of other standard beamformers in the comparison, and case 2 where the bandwidth per beam is maintained as $(M \times BW/N)$ so that the RX TMA achieves the same overall throughput as other analog/digital multibeam beamformers in the comparison. The following assumptions are made for all the architectures: 1) P_{RX} is the received power per element per beam; 2) the gain of each element is assumed to be unity; and 3) NF is the noise figure of each element up to the beamforming combiner. By analyzing the comparison data in Fig. 8, we can conclude that N -element/ M -beam analog fully connected and digital beamformers have high hardware complexities in scalable implementations, as the latter requires a sophisticated digital back-end, N high dynamic-range ADCs, and severe linearity requirements, while the former requires $M \times N$ PSs and M of N -way power combiners. On the other hand, RX TMAs can concurrently support multiple beams with low complexity in scalable beamformer implementations at either the cost of lower overall throughput (case 1), or larger

	Single-Element RX	Single-Beam Beamformer	Analog Beamformer with M Sub-Arrays	Analog Fully Connected M -Beam Beamformer	Digital M -Beam Beamformer	TMA with AM Scheme (Case-1)	TMA with AM Scheme (Case-2)
Array Number of Elements	1	N	N	N	N	N	N
Number of Elements for Each Beam	1	N	N/M	N	N	N	N
Number of Elements for Each Beam over Time	1	N	N/M	N	N	1	1
Number of Concurrent Beams	1	1	M	M	M	$N + 1$	$N + 1$
Bandwidth per Beam	BW	BW	BW	BW	BW	$\sim BW/N$	$\sim M \times BW/N$
Occupied Bandwidth after Combiner	BW	BW	BW	BW	BW	$\sim BW$	$\sim M \times BW$
Overall Throughput (# Beams \times BW per Beam)	BW	BW	$M \times BW$	$M \times BW$	$M \times BW$	$\sim BW$	$\sim M \times BW$
Signal Power per Beam after Combiner (dBm)	P_{RX}	$P_{RX} + 20 \log N$	$P_{RX} + 20 \log (N/M)$	$P_{RX} - 10 \log M + 20 \log N$	$P_{RX} + 20 \log (N)$	$\sim P_{RX}$	$\sim P_{RX}$
Noise Power per Unit BW per Beam (dBm/Hz)	$-174 + NF$	$-174 + NF + 10 \log N$	$-174 + NF + 10 \log (N/M)$	$-174 + NF - 10 \log M + 10 \log N$	$-174 + NF + 10 \log (N)$	$-174 + NF$	$-174 + NF$
Integrated Noise Power per Beam (dBm)	$-174 + NF + 10 \log BW$	$-174 + NF + 10 \log BW + 10 \log N$	$-174 + NF + 10 \log BW + 10 \log (N/M)$	$-174 + NF - 10 \log M + 10 \log BW + 10 \log N$	$-174 + NF + 10 \log BW + 10 \log (N)$	$-174 + NF + 10 \log (BW/N)$	$-174 + NF + 10 \log (\frac{M}{N} BW)$
SNR per Beam after Combiner (dB)	$P_{RX} + 174 - NF - 10 \log BW = SNR_{Base}$	$SNR_{Base} + 10 \log N$	$SNR_{Base} + 10 \log (N/M)$	$SNR_{Base} + 10 \log N$	$SNR_{Base} + 10 \log N$	$SNR_{Base} + 10 \log N$	$SNR_{Base} + 10 \log (N/M)$
Hardware Complexity	Simple	Moderate (N PSs)	Moderate (N PSs)	Complex ($M \times N$ PSs + $M \times N$ -Way Combiners)	Complex Digital-Backend & Severe Linearity Requirements & N ADCs with Larger Dynamic-Range	Simple (Switches & CLKs with Freq. \propto BW per Beam) & Larger ADC Dynamic-Range (but only 1 ADC for data demodulation)	Simple (Switches & CLKs with Freq. \propto BW per Beam) & Larger ADC Dynamic-Range (but only 1 ADC for data demodulation)

FIG. 8. Performance comparison between the RX TMA with AM scheme versus single-beam and multibeam standard RX beamformers in terms of the number of concurrent beams, the overall throughput, the SNR per beam, and the hardware complexity of each architecture.

occupied bandwidth after the combiner and slightly lower SNR per beam (case 2).

PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS OF TX TMA

The overall effective-isotropic-radiated-power (EIRP) of TX TMAs with AM and PM switching schemes can be derived with the help of the TMA array factor expressions derived in (9) and (11), respectively, by summing for all the harmonics [76]. To compare the beamforming characteristics of TX TMAs with other standard single-beam and multibeam analog/digital TX beamformers, a performance comparison is presented among these architectures in terms of the number of concurrent beams, the array gain, the EIRP, and the TX array efficiency. For this comparison, as shown in Fig. 9, six TX architectures are considered: a standard N -element single-beam beamformer, an N -element analog beamformer with M subarrays, a fully connected N -element (analog or digital) M -beam beamformer, an N -element TMA with AM scheme, an N -element TMA with PM scheme, and a TX architecture consisting of an $M \times M$ Butler matrix cascaded with an N -element TMA with PM scheme, where $M = N$. For this comparison, the following assumptions are made.

- 1) The continuously ON TX array element average power consumption is P_{dc} (in dBm).
- 2) The continuously ON TX array element is capable of generating a maximum linear average output power of P_{out} (in dBm).
- 3) The PA dominates the TX dc power consumption.
- 4) The PAPR of the data streams is neglected for simplicity.

The comparison data of the six TX architectures are presented in Fig. 10. By analyzing this data, we make the following observations. First, there exists a fundamental tradeoff between the number of concurrent beams and the EIRP per

beam for all the beamforming architectures. That is, for a given beamformer array, more beams can be supported at the fundamental cost of a lower EIRP per beam and thus lower communication distance. Second, TX TMAs offer the capability of concurrently supporting multiple beams with much lower hardware complexity than fully connected M -beam beamformers, while maintaining the same TX array efficiency, where the TX array efficiency is defined as the total EIRP (by summing for all the beams) divided by the total power consumption of the array. However, for a given array size, this comes at the cost of a lower EIRP per beam for TX TMAs.

TECHNICAL CHALLENGES AND FUTURE WORKS

In this section, we discuss two of the big challenges of TMAs and accordingly suggest some future research directions that may help with unleashing their full potential.

Fixed-Angle Beams

For MIMO applications relying on spatial multiplexing, it might be desirable to steer each of the supported beams to an arbitrary angle. With the basic switching schemes of TMAs (e.g., AM and PM), the concurrent beams they support occur at specific angles in space given by $\theta = \sin^{-1}(2n/N)$ (where $n = 0, \pm 1, \dots, \pm N/2$) for an N -element TMA. Although it is possible to steer all the beams together by simply combining the TMA with PSs as demonstrated in [74], this approach does not provide the capability of arbitrarily steering each beam separately. In addition, although the TMA reported in [82] based on the particle swarm algorithm offers harmonic beamforming capabilities, it suffers from the following limitations: 1) the optimized time-switching clocks are too complicated to be generated in practical hardware implementations as they experience arbitrary time-ON instants and different pulse widths;

FIG. 9. Architectures of the different TX beamforming systems included in the comparison.

	Single-Beam Beamformer	Analog Beamformer with M Sub-Arrays	Fully Connected M -Beam Beamformer	TMA with AM Scheme	TMA with PM Scheme	Butler Matrix + TMA with PM Scheme
Array Number of Elements	N	N	N	N	N	$M \times M$ Butler Matrix + N -Element TMA ($M = N$)
Number of Concurrent Beams	1	M	M	$N + 1$	$N + 1$	$M \times (N + 1)$
Array Gain per Beam (dB)	$10 \log N$	$10 \log (N/M)$	$10 \log N$	~ 0	~ 0	~ 0
Time-Averaged Number of ON Elements per Beam (dB)	$10 \log N$	$10 \log (N/M)$	$10 \log N$	0	$10 \log N$	$10 \log N$
EIRP per Beam (dBm)	$P_{out} + 20 \log N$	$P_{out} + 20 \log N - 20 \log M$	$P_{out} + 20 \log N - 10 \log M$	P_{out}	$P_{out} + 10 \log N$	$P_{out} + 10 \log N - 10 \log M$
TX Aggregated EIRP (dBm)	$P_{out} + 20 \log N$	$P_{out} + 20 \log N - 10 \log M$	$P_{out} + 20 \log N$	$P_{out} + 10 \log N$	$P_{out} + 20 \log N$	$P_{out} + 20 \log N$
TX Array Average Power Consumption (dBm)	$P_{DC} + 10 \log N$	$P_{DC} + 10 \log N$	$P_{DC} + 10 \log N$	P_{DC}	$P_{DC} + 10 \log N$	$P_{DC} + 10 \log N$
TX Array Efficiency (dB) (Total EIRP / Total Power Cons.)	$P_{out} - P_{DC} + 10 \log N$	$P_{out} - P_{DC} + 10 \log (N/M)$	$P_{out} - P_{DC} + 10 \log N$	$P_{out} - P_{DC} + 10 \log N$	$P_{out} - P_{DC} + 10 \log N$	$P_{out} - P_{DC} + 10 \log N$

FIG. 10. Performance comparison between TX TMAs with AM/PM schemes versus single-beam and multibeam standard TX beamformers in terms of the number of concurrent beams, the array gain, the EIRP, and the array efficiency.

and 2) it can only provide the capability of beam steering to some of the beams (i.e., it cannot arbitrarily steer all the sidebands of the TMA). A future research direction, therefore, could be to explore new approaches to engineer the TMA clocks providing arbitrary beam steering capabilities, while taking the hardware complexity into consideration.

TX Harmonics Generation

Wireless communication standards mostly impose stringent specifications on the out-of-band emissions to avoid interferences between different frequency bands. The unused sidebands generated by TX TMAs, therefore, need to be sufficiently filtered out to comply with the communication standards. Significant

research has been carried out to achieve single-sideband TMAs using optimized overlapping/nonequal-width time-modulation clocks [6], [8], [11] or by employing joint phase-time modulation where, besides time-modulation, the phases of the array elements are varied by 0° , 90° , 180° , and/or 270° as theoretically proposed in [83]. Also, advanced modulation waveform design based on stair steps approximation of sine waves has been explored for single-sideband TMAs [84], [85]. However, again, these approaches rely on complicated pulse shapes that are complicated to generate in practice, and they also eliminate all the sidebands without offering a degree of freedom to eliminate specific sidebands (while utilizing the others for MIMO operation, for example). A possible research direction, therefore, could be to

explore new low-complexity N -element TMA solutions that may be arbitrarily reconfigured to only eliminate specific sidebands.

CONCLUSION

TMA's theory, potential applications for ISAC, performance characteristics, and technical challenges are reviewed. The operation of TMAs is analyzed for different periodic switching schemes, showing that the continuously ON $0^\circ/180^\circ$ PM switching scheme may offer an enhanced array gain compared to the AM switching scheme. In addition, the double switching schemes with even/odd symmetries may be utilized to eliminate some of the array radiations (even or odd) while enhancing the array factor of the other radiations by a factor of two. The potential applications of TMAs for ISAC utilizing fully integrated implementations are discussed, including TX concurrent multibeam generation, RX multibeam reception, multibeam relays, and spatiotemporal filtering that is useful for sensing. Other TMA applications for secure communication and TX back-off efficiency enhancement are also discussed. The noise behavior of RX TMAs with an AM switching scheme is analyzed, showing that TMAs on the array-level exhibit the same noise power spectral density as the noise of a continuously ON array element. The EIRP and array efficiency are analyzed for TX TMAs, showing that they maintain the same array efficiency as other fully connected multibeam phased arrays. The technical challenges of TMAs, including their beams' fixed-angle nature and generated harmonics at TX, are discussed, showing future research directions in engineering the TMA clocks to provide degrees of freedom in eliminating the undesirable beams and/or steering the desirable beams, yet with acceptable hardware complexities to generate these clocks.

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REFERENCES

- [1] H. E. Shanks and R. W. Bickmore, "Four-dimensional electromagnetic radiators," *Can. J. Phys.*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 263–275, 1959, doi: 10.1139/p59-031
- [2] H. Shanks, "A new technique for electronic scanning," *IRE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 162–166, 1961, doi: 10.1109/TAP.1961.1144965
- [3] W. Kummer, A. Villeneuve, T. Fong, and F. Terrio, "Ultra-low sidelobes from time-modulated arrays," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 633–639, Nov. 1963, doi: 10.1109/TAP.1963.1138102
- [4] M. Johnson, "Phased-array beam steering by multiplex sampling," *Proc. IEEE*, vol. 56, no. 11, pp. 1801–1811, Nov. 1968, doi: 10.1109/PROC.1968.6754
- [5] R. S. Dixon, "Argus: A next-generation omnidirectional powerful radiotelescope," *Acta Astronaut.*, vol. 35, no. 9, pp. 745–752, 1995, doi: 10.1016/0094-5765(95)00030-4
- [6] S. Yang, Y. B. Gan, and A. Qing, "Sideband suppression in time-modulated linear arrays by the differential evolution algorithm," *IEEE Antennas Wireless Propag. Lett.*, vol. 1, pp. 173–175, 2002, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2002.807789
- [7] Fondevila, Bregains, Ares, and Moreno, "Optimizing uniformly excited linear arrays through time modulation," *IEEE Antennas Wireless Propag. Lett.*, vol. 3, pp. 298–301, 2004, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2004.838833
- [8] S. Yang, Y. B. Gan, A. Qing, and P. K. Tan, "Design of a uniform amplitude time modulated linear array with optimized time sequences," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 53, no. 7, pp. 2337–2339, Jul. 2005, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2005.850765
- [9] E. Aksoy and E. Afacan, "Thinned nonuniform amplitude time-modulated linear arrays," *IEEE Antennas Wireless Propag. Lett.*, vol. 9, pp. 514–517, 2010, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2010.2051312
- [10] R. Maneiro-Catoira, J. Brégains, J. A. García-Naya, and L. Castedo, "Time-modulated arrays with sum of weighted cosine pulses," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Symp. Antennas Propag. (APSURSI)*, 2016, pp. 697–698, doi: 10.1109/APS.2016.7696057
- [11] L. Poli, P. Rocca, L. Manica, and A. Massa, "Handling sideband radiations in time-modulated arrays through particle swarm optimization," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 58, no. 4, pp. 1408–1411, Apr. 2010, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2010.2041165
- [12] F. Yang et al., "Synthesis of low-sidelobe 4-D heterogeneous antenna arrays including mutual coupling using iterative convex optimization," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 68, no. 1, pp. 329–340, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2019.2947153
- [13] F. Yang et al., "Complete and unified time- and frequency-domain study on 4-D antenna arrays including mutual coupling effect," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 68, no. 2, pp. 824–837, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2019.2943393
- [14] Y.-X. Zhang, Y.-C. Jiao, and L. Zhang, "Efficient directivity maximization of time-modulated arrays with two-stage convex optimization," *IEEE Antennas Wireless Propag. Lett.*, vol. 19, no. 11, pp. 1847–1851, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2020.2989826
- [15] A. B. Siddharth Pal and S. Das, "Design of time-modulated linear arrays with a multi-objective optimization approach," *Prog. Electromagn. Res. B*, vol. 23, pp. 83–107, 2010, doi: 10.2528/PIERB10052401
- [16] T. Nakanishi, K. Kihira, T. Takahashi, Y. Konishi, and I. Chiba, "Sideband suppression using switched phase distribution in time-modulated array antennas," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Symp. Phased Array Syst. Technol.*, 2013, pp. 521–528, doi: 10.1109/ARRAY.2013.6731882
- [17] G. Ram, D. Mandal, M. A. Panduro, R. Kar, and Z. Raida, "Optimal design of timed antenna arrays for SLL reduction, dual and multiple broad nulls in the radiation pattern," *IETE Tech. Rev.*, vol. 37, no. 6, pp. 622–631, 2020, doi: 10.1080/02564602.2019.1699453
- [18] E. Aksoy and E. Afacan, "Calculation of sideband power radiation in time-modulated arrays with asymmetrically positioned pulses," *IEEE Antennas Wireless Propag. Lett.*, vol. 11, pp. 133–136, 2012, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2012.2185916
- [19] J. Yang, W.-T. Li, X.-W. Shi, L. Xin, and J.-F. Yu, "A hybrid ABC-DE algorithm and its application for time-modulated arrays pattern synthesis," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 61, no. 11, pp. 5485–5495, Nov. 2013, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2013.2279093
- [20] G. Ni, C. He, J. Chen, Y. Liu, and R. Jin, "Low sideband radiation beam scanning at carrier frequency for time-modulated array by non-uniform period modulation," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 68, no. 5, pp. 3695–3704, May 2020, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2020.2969889
- [21] G. Ram, R. Kar, D. Mandal, and S. P. Ghoshal, "Optimal design of linear antenna arrays of dipole elements using flower pollination algorithm," *IETE J. Res.*, vol. 65, no. 5, pp. 694–701, 2019, doi: 10.1080/03772063.2018.1452639
- [22] A. Chakraborty, G. Ram, and D. Mandal, "Pattern synthesis of timed antenna array with the exploitation and suppression of harmonic radiation," *Int. J. Commun. Syst.*, vol. 34, no. 4, 2021, Art. no. e4727, doi: 10.1002/dac.4727
- [23] L. P. Paolo Rocca and M. D'Urso, "An iterative approach for the synthesis of optimized sparse time-modulated linear arrays," *Prog. Electromagn. Res. B*, vol. 55, pp. 365–382, 2013, doi: 10.2528/PIERB13072801
- [24] C. He, H. Yu, X. Liang, J. Geng, and R. Jin, "Sideband radiation level suppression in time-modulated array by nonuniform period modulation," *IEEE Antennas Wireless Propag. Lett.*, vol. 14, pp. 606–609, 2015, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2014.2373639
- [25] A. Das, D. Mandal, and R. Kar, "An optimal time modulated compact circular antenna array design using a stochastic optimization technique," *J. Electromagn. Waves Appl.*, vol. 35, no. 8, pp. 1025–1045, 2021, doi: 10.1080/09205071.2020.1868353
- [26] A. Chakraborty, G. Ram, and D. Mandal, "Optimal pulse shifting in timed antenna array for simultaneous reduction of sidelobe and sideband level," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 131063–131075, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3010047

- [27] Y. Ma, C. Miao, Y.-H. Li, and W. Wu, "A partition-based method for harmonic beamforming of time-modulated planar array," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 69, no. 4, pp. 2112–2121, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2020.3026893
- [28] S. Yang and Z. Nie, "Time modulated planar arrays with square lattices and circular boundaries," *Int. J. Numer. Modell. Electron. Netw. Devices Fields*, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 469–480, 2005, doi: 10.1002/jnm.592
- [29] L. Poli, P. Rocca, L. Manica, and A. Massa, "Time modulated planar arrays – analysis and optimisation of the sideband radiations," *IET Microwaves, Antennas Propag.*, vol. 4, pp. 1165–1171, 2010, doi: 10.1049/iet-map.2009.0379
- [30] E. Aksoy and E. Afacan, "An inequality for the calculation of relative maximum sideband level in time-modulated linear and planar arrays," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 62, no. 6, pp. 3392–3397, Jun. 2014, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2014.2311470
- [31] G. Li, S. Yang, M. Huang, and Z. Nie, "Sidelobe suppression in time modulated linear arrays with unequal element spacing," *J. Electromagn. Waves Appl.*, vol. 24, no. 5–6, pp. 775–783, 2010, doi: 10.1163/156939310791036368
- [32] L. Zheng, S. Yang, and Z. Nie, "Pattern synthesis with specified broad nulls in time-modulated circular antenna arrays," *Electromagnetics*, vol. 31, no. 5, pp. 355–367, 2011, doi: 10.1080/02726343.2011.579770
- [33] G. Ram, D. Mandal, R. Kar, and S. P. Ghoshal, "Cat swarm optimization as applied to time-modulated concentric circular antenna array: Analysis and comparison with other stochastic optimization methods," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 63, no. 9, pp. 4180–4183, Sep. 2015, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2015.2444439
- [34] A. Durmus and R. Kurban, "Optimal synthesis of concentric circular antenna arrays using political optimizer," *IETE J. Res.*, vol. 68, no. 1, pp. 768–777, 2022, doi: 10.1080/03772063.2021.1902871
- [35] J. Euzière, R. Guinvarc'h, B. Uguen, and R. Gillard, "Optimization of sparse time-modulated array by genetic algorithm for radar applications," *IEEE Antennas Wireless Propag. Lett.*, vol. 13, pp. 161–164, 2014, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2014.2299285
- [36] W. Wu, Q. Chen, J.-D. Zhang, T. Huang, and D.-G. Fang, "Time modulated array antennas: A review," *Electromagn. Sci.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 1–19, 2024, doi: 10.23919/emsci.2023.0043
- [37] P. Rocca, G. Oliveri, R. J. Mailloux, and A. Massa, "Unconventional phased array architectures and design methodologies—A review," *Proc. IEEE*, vol. 104, no. 3, pp. 544–560, Mar. 2016, doi: 10.1109/JPROC.2015.2512389
- [38] A.-M. Yao, P. Rocca, W. Wu, A. Massa, and D.-G. Fang, "Synthesis of time-modulated frequency diverse arrays for short-range multifocusing," *IEEE J. Sel. Topics Signal Process.*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 282–294, Mar. 2017, doi: 10.1109/JSTSP.2016.2615267
- [39] W. C. Barott and B. Himed, "Time-modulated array pattern for sidelobe blanking in spectrometry and radar," *IEEE Antennas Wireless Propag. Lett.*, vol. 13, pp. 1015–1018, 2014, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2014.2323351
- [40] D.-G. Fang, A.-M. Yao, and W. Wu, "Synthesis of 4-D beampatterns using 4-D arrays," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Symp. Antennas Propag. (APSURSI)*, 2016, pp. 703–704, doi: 10.1109/APS.2016.7696060
- [41] D. Ni, S. Yang, Y. Chen, and J. Guo, "A study on the application of subarrayed time-modulated arrays to MIMO radar," *IEEE Antennas Wireless Propag. Lett.*, vol. 16, pp. 1171–1174, 2017, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2016.2626478
- [42] A. Tennant and B. Allen, "Generation of OAM radio waves using circular time-switched array antenna," *Electron. Lett.*, vol. 48, pp. 1365–1366, 2012, doi: 10.1049/el.2012.2664
- [43] P.-Y. Feng, S.-W. Qu, and S. Yang, "OAM-generating transmitarray antenna with circular phased array antenna feed," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 68, no. 6, pp. 4540–4548, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2020.2972393
- [44] C. He et al., "Direction finding by time-modulated linear array," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 66, no. 7, pp. 3642–3652, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2018.2835164
- [45] J. Guo, S. Yang, S.-W. Qu, J. Hu, and Z. Nie, "A study on linear frequency modulation signal transmission by 4-D antenna arrays," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 63, no. 12, pp. 5409–5416, Dec. 2015, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2015.2493559
- [46] G. Ni, C. He, J. Chen, L. Bai, and R. Jin, "Direction finding and performance analysis with 1 bit time modulated array," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 69, no. 10, pp. 6881–6893, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2021.3076297
- [47] K. Chen et al., "Efficient secure communication in 4-D antenna arrays through joint space–time modulation," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 70, no. 8, pp. 7046–7056, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2022.3161488
- [48] C. Qu et al., "A vector modulation approach for secure communications based on 4-D antenna arrays," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 70, no. 5, pp. 3723–3732, May 2022, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2021.3137246
- [49] D. Masotti, A. Costanzo, M. Del Prete, and V. Rizzoli, "Time-modulation of linear arrays for real-time reconfigurable wireless power transmission," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 64, no. 2, pp. 331–342, Feb. 2016, doi: 10.1109/TMTT.2015.2512275
- [50] Y.-Q. Yang, H. Wang, and Y.-X. Guo, "A time-modulated array with digitally preprocessed rectangular pulses for wireless power transmission," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 68, no. 4, pp. 3283–3288, 2020, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2019.2930135
- [51] C. He, X. Liang, J. Geng, and R. Jin, "Parallel calibration method for phased array with harmonic characteristic analysis," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 62, no. 10, pp. 5029–5036, Oct. 2014, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2014.2341700
- [52] B. Sadhu et al., "A 28-GHz 32-element TRX phased-array IC with concurrent dual-polarized operation and orthogonal phase and gain control for 5G communications," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 52, no. 12, pp. 3373–3391, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1109/JSSC.2017.2766211
- [53] J. Pang et al., "A CMOS dual-polarized phased-array beamformer utilizing cross-polarization leakage cancellation for 5G MIMO systems," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 56, no. 4, pp. 1310–1326, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1109/JSSC.2020.3045258
- [54] A. Khalil et al., "2.1 mm-Wave 5G radios: Baseband to waves," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Solid-State Circuits Conf. (ISSCC) Dig. Tech. Papers*, vol. 64, Feb. 2021, pp. 38–40, doi: 10.1109/ISSCC42613.2021.9365980
- [55] J. D. Dunworth et al., "A 28GHz bulk-CMOS dual-polarization phased-array transceiver with 24 channels for 5G user and basestation equipment," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Solid-State Circuits Conf. (ISSCC) Dig. Tech. Papers*, Feb. 2018, pp. 70–72, doi: 10.1109/ISSCC.2018.8310188
- [56] K. Kibaroglu, M. Sayginer, T. Phelps, and G. M. Rebeiz, "A 64-element 28-GHz phased-array transceiver with 52-dBm EIRP and 8–12-Gb/s 5G link at 300 meters without any calibration," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 66, no. 12, pp. 5796–5811, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TMTT.2018.2854174
- [57] M. Eleraky, J. Park, B. A. Abdelmagid, N. S. Mannem, and H. Wang, "A mm-Wave phase-time co-apertured transceiver array with beam squinting mitigation for wideband beamforming/spatial-nulling," in *Proc. IEEE Custom Integr. Circuits Conf.*, Apr. 2024, pp. 1–2, doi: 10.1109/CICC60959.2024.10528972.
- [58] N. Li et al., "A Ka-band 64-element four-beam phased array receiver with inter-beam interference cancellation," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 73, no. 1, pp. 221–233, Jan. 2025, doi: 10.1109/TMTT.2024.3418879
- [59] H. Gao et al., "A Ka-band four-beam high-linearity transmitter with beam interference cancellation for SATCOM multibeam communication," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 73, no. 4, pp. 2009–2022, Apr. 2025, doi: 10.1109/TMTT.2025.3542097
- [60] Y. Kim et al., "A co-integrated optical phased array, Mach-Zehnder modulator and mm-Wave driver for free-space communication," in *Proc. IEEE Custom Integr. Circuits Conf.*, 2024, pp. 1–2, doi: 10.1109/CICC60959.2024.10529031.
- [61] Y. Kim et al., "Monolithically integrated optical phased array for optical wireless communication," *J. Lightw. Technol.*, vol. 42, no. 23, pp. 8181–8190, 2024, doi: 10.1109/JLT.2024.3425521
- [62] M. Elkhouly et al., "Fully integrated 2D scalable TX/RX chipset for D-band phased-array-on-glass modules," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Solid-State Circuits Conf. (ISSCC) Dig. Tech. Papers*, vol. 65, Feb. 2022, pp. 76–78, doi: 10.1109/ISSCC42614.2022.9731626
- [63] A. Karakuzulu, W. A. Ahmad, D. Kissinger, and A. Malignaggi, "A four-channel bidirectional D-band phased-array transceiver for 200 Gb/s 6G wireless communications in a 130-nm BiCMOS technology," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 58, no. 5, pp. 1310–1322, May 2023, doi: 10.1109/JSSC.2022.3232948

- [64] D. del Rio et al., "A D-Band 16-element phased-array transceiver in 55-nm BiCMOS," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 71, no. 2, pp. 854–869, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1109/TMTT.2022.3203709
- [65] B. A. Abdelmagid, B. Lin, and H. Wang, "A D-band 2D-scalable 4×4 active reflective relay with orthogonally polarized on-chip TX/RX antennas and in-front-end common-centroid fast azimuth/elevation angle-of-arrival detection," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Solid-State Circuits Conf. (ISSCC) Dig. Tech. Papers*, vol. 68, Feb. 2025, pp. 206–208, doi: 10.1109/ISSCC49661.2025.10904706
- [66] A. Asoodeh and M. Atarodi, "A full 360° vector-sum phase shifter with very low RMS phase error over a wide bandwidth," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 60, no. 6, pp. 1626–1634, Jun. 2012, doi: 10.1109/TMTT.2012.2189227
- [67] B. A. Abdelmagid, Y. Liu, H. Wang, and A. Wideband, "Bidirectional calibration-free frequency/switching staggering 360° D-band phase shifter with frequency-invariant codes achieving $\lt;2.38^\circ/0.63\text{dB}$ RMS-errors over 24% bandwidth," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Solid-State Circuits Conf. (ISSCC) Dig. Tech. Papers*, vol. 68, Feb. 2025, pp. 548–550, doi: 10.1109/ISSCC49661.2025.10904552
- [68] C.-S. Lin, S.-F. Chang, C.-C. Chang, and Y.-H. Shu, "Design of a reflection-type phase shifter with wide relative phase shift and constant insertion loss," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 55, no. 9, pp. 1862–1868, Sep. 2007, doi: 10.1109/TMTT.2007.903346
- [69] B. A. Abdelmagid and H. Wang, "An ultra-compact and wideband transformer-based coupler with arbitrary phase difference and arbitrary power division ratio," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 72, no. 2, pp. 1133–1147, Feb. 2024, doi: 10.1109/TMTT.2023.3298191
- [70] B. A. Abdelmagid and H. Wang, "A compact 48–63 GHz 3-dB transformer-based quadrature coupler with arbitrary transformer coupling coefficient in 22-nm CMOS FDSOI," *IEEE Microw. Wireless Compon. Lett.*, vol. 34, no. 10, pp. 1155–1157, Oct. 2024, doi: 10.1109/LMWT.2024.3443771
- [71] M. Elkholy, S. Shakib, J. Dunworth, V. Aparin, and K. Entesari, "A wideband variable gain LNA with high OIP3 for 5G using 40-nm bulk CMOS," *IEEE Microw. Wireless Compon. Lett.*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 64–66, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1109/LMWC.2017.2779832
- [72] B. Sadhu, J. F. Bulzacchelli, and A. Valdes-Garcia, "A 28GHz SiGe BiCMOS phase invariant VGA," in *Proc. IEEE Radio Freq. Integr. Circuits Symp. (RFIC)*, 2016, pp. 150–153, doi: 10.1109/RFIC.2016.7508273.
- [73] Y. Yi, D. Zhao, and X. You, "A Ka-band CMOS digital-controlled phase-invariant variable gain amplifier with 4-bit tuning range and 0.5-dB resolution," in *Proc. IEEE Radio Freq. Integr. Circuits Symp. (RFIC)*, 2018, pp. 152–155, doi: 10.1109/RFIC.2018.8428833.
- [74] T.-Y. Huang, B. Lin, N. S. Mannem, B. Abdelaziz, and H. Wang, "A time-modulated concurrent steerable multibeam MIMO receiver array with spectral-spatial mapping using one beamformer and single-wire interface," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 58, no. 5, pp. 1228–1240, May 2023, doi: 10.1109/JSSC.2023.3253793
- [75] Y. Zhang et al., "A 28GHz 4-stream time-division MIMO phased-array receiver utilizing Nyquist-rate fast beam switching for 5G and beyond," in *Proc. IEEE Symp. VLSI Technol. Circuits (VLSI)*, 2024, pp. 1–2, doi: 10.1109/VLSITechnologyandCir46783.2024.10631537.
- [76] K.-S. Choi, B. A. Abdelmagid, Y. Liu, and H. Wang, "A D-band concurrent 20-beam MIMO transmitter array with a four-element joint static/dynamic beam-multiplication beamformer," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 60, no. 6, pp. 1906–1920, Jun. 2025, doi: 10.1109/JSSC.2024.3487619
- [77] B. A. Abdelmagid, K.-S. Choi, Y. Kim, and H. Wang, "A D-band scalable and LO-less time-modulated multibeam active relay array with broadcasting capability for 6G distributed MIMO networks," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, early access, May 2025, doi: 10.1109/TMTT.2025.3568127
- [78] X. Lu, S. Venkatesh, B. Tang, and K. Sengupta, "Physical layer security through directional modulation with spatio-temporal millimeter-wave transmitter arrays," *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 59, no. 9, pp. 2831–2847, Sep. 2024, doi: 10.1109/JSSC.2024.3384373
- [79] X. Huang et al., "A fully-connected time-modulated phased-array transmitter featuring physical security directional link and multi-beam PAPR reduction," in *Proc. IEEE Asian Solid-State Circuits Conf. (A-SSCC)*, 2024, pp. 1–3, doi: 10.1109/A-SSCC60305.2024.10849177
- [80] Y. Zhao et al., "Spatial-temporal direct-digital beamforming power amplifier with enhanced back-off efficiency in a 24GHz phased array," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Solid-State Circuits Conf. (ISSCC) Dig. Tech. Papers*, vol. 68, 2025, pp. 1–3, doi: 10.1109/ISSCC49661.2025.10904527
- [81] A. Paidimarri and B. Sadhu, "Spatio-temporal filtering: Precise beam control using fast beam switching," in *Proc. IEEE Radio Freq. Integr. Circuits Symp. (RFIC)*, 2020, pp. 207–210, doi: 10.1109/RFIC49505.2020.9218275.
- [82] L. Poli, P. Rocca, G. Oliveri, and A. Massa, "Harmonic beamforming in time-modulated linear arrays," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 59, no. 7, pp. 2538–2545, Jul. 2011, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2011.2152323
- [83] A.-M. Yao, W. Wu, and D.-G. Fang, "Single-sideband time-modulated phased array," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 63, no. 5, pp. 1957–1968, May 2015, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2015.2406890
- [84] Q. Chen, J.-D. Zhang, W. Wu, and D.-G. Fang, "A single-sideband time-modulated phased array with low sideband level suitable for wide-bandwidth signals," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 70, no. 2, pp. 1057–1067, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2021.3111322
- [85] Q. Chen, J.-D. Zhang, D.-Y. Luo, W. Wu, Y. Yu, and D.-G. Fang, "Low-sidelobe single-sideband time-modulated phased array using stepped waveforms with different amplitudes," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 71, no. 12, pp. 9643–9654, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2023.3313669

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